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HIGH GAS BARRIER PROPERTIES OF POLYMER/MOS₂ NANOSHEET NANOCOMPOSITES

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Importance of Gas Barrier Performance

- Lightweight polymers and composites are used widely in packaging
- Polymers have insufficient gas barrier property for gas storage or food preservation
- The adoption of nanosheets in the polymer matrix can maximising the gas diffusion path
- Impermeable nanoclays, graphene oxide and graphene nanosheets have been applied to enhance gas barrier property

Image from <http://basalt.today/2017/10/13318/>

Two Dimensional Layered Nanomaterials

Common features

- Intra-layer bonds are typically covalent, coupled by weak van der Waals forces
- 2DLMs refer to single layer or few-layer of these materials
- Overwhelming research interests since single-layer Graphene was found in 2004
- Mechanical exfoliation and liquid phase exfoliation can be used for preparing monolayer or few-layer 2DLMs

Graphs from Wang et al. Adv Funct Mater, 27 (2017) 1604134

Broad Applications of 2D Layered Nanomaterials and their Nanocomposites

Images from Google Images search

Materials and Methods

- PVA (molecular weight 89,000-98,000, 99+% hydrolyzed)
- Hexagonal molybdenum disulfide powder (Sigma Aldrich)
- Ball-mill method for preparation of exfoliated MoS₂ nanosheets
- Hydroxyl-functionalized MoS₂ dispersion was obtained
- Film casting was used for preparation of nanocomposites
- Characterisations are gas permeance tests, thermal conductivity and diffusivity, tensile properties, TGA, morphological

Polymer Nanocomposites with MoS₂ Nanosheets

Gas Barrier Properties

Polymer Nanocomposites with MoS₂ Nanosheets

Tensile Properties

Polymer Nanocomposites with MoS₂ Nanosheets

Thermal Diffusivity and Thermal Conductivity

- Anisotropic thermal conductivity: In-plane is almost 10 times of the cross-plane properties
- Comparable results with the PVA/BNNS nanocomposite films
- At the BNNS content of 0.8 wt%, the PVA nanocomposite had a cross-plane thermal conductivity of 0.39 W/m·K and an in-plane thermal conductivity of 1.72 W/m·K

Polymer Nanocomposites with MoS₂ Nanosheets

Optical Properties

- Compared with the low light absorption intensity of PVA, the PVA/MoS₂ nanocomposite films showed enhanced UV absorption in the wavelength range of 200–400 nm
- In the UVB and UVC region, the light absorption intensity increased significantly as the nanofiller content increased from 0 to 0.75 vol%

Conclusions

- PVA/MoS₂ nanocomposite is multifunctional
- With low loading (<1wt%) of hydroxy-functionalized MoS₂ nanosheets, 95% reduction of helium permeability was realised
- Tensile elongation at break and toughness increased 140% and 130%
- Thermal conductivity was significantly improved
- Hydrogen bonding was found between the hydroxyl-functionalized MoS₂ nanosheets and PVA